

SOCIAL PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS OF INTER-PERSONAL RELATIONS IN THE EXAMPLE OF ADOLESCENTS

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Abstract: *This article presents the social psychological factors of interpersonal relationships with adolescents, which are the most important condition for personal development. It is well known that adolescence is the most difficult period. This is a turning point in everyone's life. For some people, this period is almost imperceptible, while for others it is a period of emotional and mood swings. Almost every teenager faces problems such as increased tendency to quarrel with other people, behavioral problems in the family and at school: depression, suicide attempts, lack of friends and misunderstanding of each other, deviant behavior and others. It should also be noted that adolescence is a period of adolescent personality, their will, self-esteem, self-awareness and character formation. This happens during a hormonal explosion that occurs in a teenager's body. The main stage of the formation of interpersonal relationships also occurs during adolescence. The basis of interpersonal relationships is the relationship of individuals to each other. Although the need for communication arises in early childhood, this need increases during adolescence. A teenager's entire life is based on communication, communication with peers or adults. Therefore, problems with interpersonal relationships do not lose their relevance. Therefore, problems with interpersonal relationships do not lose their relevance.*

Keywords: *Adolescence, peers, identification, sensory-motor effects.*

Adolescence is a period of transition from childhood to adulthood. This is the period when childhood ends. It is a period of life in which the development of the individual, the formation of character and self-esteem occurs most rapidly. The center of a teenager's life becomes communication with peers. Adolescence is not only a period of transition, but also a period of crisis. The crisis of adolescence has always attracted many scientists. This unexplained mood change is accompanied by an increase in feelings about self-esteem, especially appearance or ability. Adolescents may feel sensitive and rude or shy and rude. Teenagers show their independence, their rejection of authority and rules. Many authors believe that the crisis of adolescents is associated with a new level of self-awareness. "Self-awareness is formed in adolescents based on the analysis and evaluation of their own behavior and activities"

At the beginning of adolescence, children develop a desire to be like adults. Teenagers want to feel like adults and be treated the same. On the one hand, parents

are really starting to accept children as adults. For example, they may consult with them on daily matters or allow them to walk longer with their friends. But on the other hand, teenagers may not be able to meet all the requirements that adults place on them. Adolescents lack such qualities as independence, seriousness, and responsibility. That's why it's still impossible to treat him like an adult. All teenagers want to be like adults. This desire leads them to external and internal changes. "

Leadership activities also change during adolescence. Intimate and personal communication with peers comes as a learning activity. But at the same time, educational activities are not going anywhere; it simply goes into the background. Communication for teenagers is an information channel through which they learn social principles, ethical norms and rules, establish relationships with each other. Adolescents have two systems of relationships. The first is with adults; the other with peers. Relationships with adults are formed unequally, on the contrary, with peers. At the end of adolescence, there is a need for a close friend. Sometimes teenagers want to believe, to tell all the secrets. A close friend should keep them, be sensitive and careful. Adolescence is shaped around a personality crisis. All the changes in a teenager's self-awareness are of great importance for his or her development. Specificity is a feature of the human mind that is manifested in the ability of a person to express belonging to different groups. If a child is unable to achieve their identity, it will lead to a crisis. The basis of personality formation is personal self-determination.

Adolescence opens up a whole new world for the child, including the inner world. There is the ability to be self-aware - a personal reflection. In this regard, the teenager begins to ask himself many questions: Who am I? Do I like others? Would you like to talk to me? But a teenager cannot answer all of these questions correctly. Only in his late teens can he do that. Throughout the period, the adolescent learns about himself, his feelings, motives, values, abilities, and hobbies. In this way, the adolescent develops self-awareness. During adolescence, the relationship between a boy and a girl begins to change. There is an interest in the opposite sex. So they start paying more attention to their appearance. During adulthood, there can be a romantic relationship between a boy and a girl. They can take notes, have meetings, go to the movies together. As a result, teenagers begin to perfect themselves to please each other. "Physiological development ensures sexual desire between a boy and a girl, which is characterized by increased arousal.

Adolescents are increasingly beginning to dedicate themselves to self-education. Much attention is paid to the development of volitional traits during adulthood. For example, boys begin to spend more time in sports to develop endurance and strength. Adolescence is a difficult time. It is a manifestation of stubbornness and willpower. It's time for personal identification. This period prepares the child for the next life as a conscious person capable of making choices and drawing conclusions. Families and teachers have a big impact on children. The impact of any adult on a child is clearly visible. Adults for children - a source of auditory, tactile, sensory-motor effects. The

child finds help and support in communicating with adults. Adults enrich children with experience and set tasks for them to acquire new skills.

Conclusion: Analyzing the theoretical material on the social psychological problem of interpersonal relationships in adolescence, studying psychological features, we came to the conclusion that all psychological changes occur against the background of puberty and changes in the anatomical and physiological structure of the body. There will be some changes during this period. They have new sensations such as a sense of maturity, self-awareness, reflection, willpower, and so on. The leading activity of adolescents is close and personal communication with peers. Communication for teens is about building relationships with others. The ability to communicate properly is a prerequisite for the normal development of adolescents in society. During adolescence, two systems of relationships develop: with adults and with peers. Sometimes these two systems contradict each other.

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